

Synthesis and Characterization of Soluble Pyridinium Containing Copolyimides

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Novel cationic copolyimides of ionene type based on 4,4'-oxydiphthalic anhydride (ODPA) and 4,4'-(1,4-phenylenediisopropylidene)bisaniline (BIS P), and 2,6 – diaminopyridine (DAP) were synthesized. The copolyimides were obtained in two stages: first the copolyimides with 0/1; 0.2/0.8; 0.3/0.7; 0.5/0.5; 0.6/0.4 and 1/0 DAP/Bis P ratio were obtained by thermal imidization, then the quaternization of soluble copolyimides with methyl iodide was carried out for 24 or 48h. The samples were characterized via FTIR, NMR and EDX methods to confirm the structure and composition. The cationic copolyimides with the content of DAP less than 0.3 showed the initial weight loss (onset) around 250°C according to TGA results and demonstrated solubility in chloroform. The highest ionic conductivity value 0.234 S cm⁻¹ showed the sample with 0.3 DAP content and 0.17 degree of quaternization. The stability of the membranes in alkaline media was evaluated by FTIR and TGA. It was shown that the samples with content of DAP more than 0.3 lost their integrity probably due to partial hydrolysis of imide rings, while copolyimides with DAP content 0.2 and 0.3 remained stable.

1. Introduction

Hydrogen (H₂) emerges as a promising energy solution for industrial applications, transportation and households, offering versatile storage options for short-, medium-, and long-term energy needs. Electrochemical water splitting stands out as a well-established method for generating pure H₂ (1), (2), (3), (4). Among various water electrolysis (WE) technologies, anion exchange membrane water electrolysis (AEM WE) holds particular significance, though it remains mainly laboratory technology compared to alkaline water electrolysis (AWE) and proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEM WE). Over the

past two decades, research interest in advancing AEM WE technology has urged significantly (5), (6), (7).

Anion exchange membrane (AEM) represents an important part of AEM WE. To be effective AEM must meet specific criteria: i) it should facilitate the efficient separation of hydrogen and oxygen produced at the electrodes, ii) possess a high ion-exchange capacity, iii) exhibit non-permeability to electrons, iv) demonstrate robust mechanical stability, and v) ionic conductivity greater than 0.1 Scm^{-1} along with vi) resistance to degradation in alkaline media (8),(9),(10).

PolymerAEMs typically consist of a polymer backbone, responsible for key properties such as mechanical strength, thermal resistance, swelling behaviour, and water absorption, along with cations attached as pendant groups to the main polymer chain, contributing to ion conductivity. Considering that degradation in alkaline environments can result from both polymer chain breakdown and cation destruction, selecting a polymer with an alkali-resistant backbone is crucial (11), (12)

Among the polymers commonly employed in AEMs, poly(arylene ether) and poly(phenylene) are frequently utilized, alongside poly(ethylene), while block or random copolymers like polystyrene-*b*-poly(ethylene/butylene)-*b*-polystyrene also find application(13),(14),(15),(16). Synthesis of such polymers often involves chloromethylation followed by quaternization. However, chloromethylation encounters a significant obstacle due to the carcinogenic properties of the conventional chloromethylating agent (17). Regarding this, one of the more appealing alternatives involves post-polymerization quaternization of polymers containing either tertiary amines or nitrogen-containing heterocyclic fragments in the main chain.

Nevertheless, polymers for AEMs are not only those with cationic functional groups attached to the pendant chain but also those with charges embedded within the polymer backbone (18). Recent studies, such as (19), dealing with the influence of ion positioning on both ionic conductivity and stability, have unveiled that ionene-type polymers demonstrate higher conductivity and prolonged alkaline stability comparing to ionomers which bear cation in pendants (20), (21), (22).

Aromatic polyimides (PIs) are renowned for their exceptional thermal stability, resistance to solvents, and mechanical strength (23), (24), (25), (26). Recently, polyimide-based ionenes gained considerable attention as promising polymers for use as AEMs in various processes, including electro dialysis, fuel cells, electrolyzers. For instance, in a study (27) imidazolium containing polyimide ionene is reported, and pyridinium containing polyimides were

developed (28). It is well known that pyridinium exhibits lower stability in alkaline media than trimethyl ammonium or imidazolium (29), (30) due to the hydroxide attack in *ortho* position and as a result the loss of positive charges, which are needed for the transport of hydroxide anions. However, pyridinium-containing polymer AEMs show rather high alkaline stability when *ortho* position (2,6) of pyridine are occupied thus preventing the OH⁻ attack (31), (32), (33).

This work aims to synthesize soluble polyimide-based ionenes for AEM WE containing pyridinium in the main chain. To our knowledge, this type of materials was synthesized for electro dialysis operation, but were not prepared for application in membrane alkaline water electrolysis. To synthesize desired polyimide-based ionenes, we choose the post-polymerization modification of copolyimides (coPIs) *via* Menshutkin reaction of coPI containing pyridine fragments with alkyl halides. Aromatic PIs generally show poor solubility in organic solvents due to strong inter-chain interactions of imide rings. The introduction of methyl substituent into backbone can enhance the solubility of PI as it was shown in(34).To synthesize soluble coPI we initially selected a polyimide based on 4,4'-oxydiphtalic anhydride (ODPA) and 4,4'-(1,4-phenylenediisopropylidene)bisaniline (BIS P), which was reported to possess excellent thermal and mechanical properties as well as solubility in chloroform(35), as well as outstanding film forming ability. In this research we synthesized a series of copolyimides containing pyridine moieties using 2,6-diaminopyridine as one of the monomers. The obtained polyimides were then quaternized and evaluated regarding their thermal properties, alkaline stability, and ion conductivity.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

4,4'-Oxydiphtalic anhydride (ODPA) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich and dried in vacuum at 160°C for 5 h before use. Bisaniline P (BIS P, 4,4'-(1,4-phenylenediisopropylidene)bisaniline) (Mitsui PI), 2,6-diaminopyridine (DAP), methyl iodide, N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) purchased from Merck and dimethylformamide (DMF) and diethyl ether purchased from Lachner were used as received.

2.2. Synthesis

PIs and random coPIs were synthesized in two stages (Scheme 1). First, the dianhydride (ODPA) (2 g, 6.4 mmol) was reacted with either BIS P, DAP or their mixture in NMP under

N_2 atmosphere which resulted in formation of the corresponding polyamic acid (PAA) solution in NMP. Samples with the following molar ratio of components: ODPAs:BIS P:DAPas 1:1:0; 1:0,8:0,2; 1:0,7:0,3; 1:0,5:0,5; 1:0,4:0,6 were prepared. The resulting 10_{w/w%} solution was stirred under inert atmosphere (N_2) for 12h. After this period the PAA was cast on the glass substrate, and during the second stage the thermal imidization was fulfilled according to the procedure: 60°C – 24h, 100°C – 1h, 150°C – 1h, 200°C – 1h, 250°C – 0.5h. The following samples of coPIs were obtained: DAP-0, DAP-0.2, DAP-0.3, DAP-0.5, DAP-0.6, where 0; 0.2; 0.3; 0.5 and 0.6 corresponds to pyridine content. Soluble coPIs (0.5 g) were redissolved in DMF (20 mL) at heating, then excess of the methyl iodide (20 eq.) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed at 70°C for 24h or 48h then precipitated in diethyl ether, filtered off, washed with diethyl ether, and dried. The different times of the reflux were used in order to evaluate the influence of the reaction time on degree of substitution (DS). The following samples of modified coPIs were synthesized DAP-0.2Q, DAP-0.3Q, DAP-0.5Q (after 24h) and DAP-0.2Q2, DAP-0.3Q2 (after 48h). The membranes were cast on glass substrate from the solution of the polymer in $CHCl_3$.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of random copolyimides and their modification

coPI: 1H NMR: (500 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 1.75 (12H, s), 7.2 (4H, s), 7.35–7.37 (4H, d), 7.4–7.42 (4H, d), 7.47–7.51 (4H, m), 7.56–7.62 (6H, m), 8.01–8.05 (4H, m), 8.10–8.13 (1H, t).

coPI-Q: 1H NMR: (500 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 1.75 (12H, s), 3.5 (3H, s), 7.2 (4H, s), 7.35–7.37 (4H, d), 7.4–7.42 (4H, d), 7.47–7.51 (4H, m), 7.56–7.62 (6H, m), 8.01–8.05 (4H, m), 8.10–8.13 (1H, t).

2.3. Characterization

^1H NMR spectra of polymers were measured on a 500 MHz Bruker Avance 500 spectrometer in CDCl_3 at 25°C . FTIR spectra were recorded with the help of a Nicolet 6700 FTIR-spectrometer (Thermo-Nicolet) in the ATR mode (wavenumber range $4000 - 600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). DSC analyses were performed on TA Instruments (Discovery DSC250 auto) calorimeter. Temperature range was from 20°C to 400°C , temperature rate $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ and N_2 flow 50 mL min^{-1} . The curves from the second heating run were analyzed. TGA measurements were performed on TA Instruments (TGA550 Auto Advanced) with the heating rate $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ in N_2 atmosphere. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were taken using a MIRA 3 (Tescan GmbH, Czech Republic) microscope operating at 10 keV. The SEM images of the surface and cross-section of the membrane were obtained. The cross-section was prepared by cutting the membrane perpendicularly to its edge with a blade to prevent mechanical deformation. To improve image quality and reduce charging effects, a 6 nm layer of platinum was sputtered onto the sample surface using a Kurt-Lesker magnetron sputtering system. Chemical composition mapping analysis was carried out using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) with a Bruker XFlash detector mounted directly into the SEM, with electron beam energy of 10 keV. The calculation of the elemental compositions was based on measurements taken from five scans at five different places of the samples. The solubility of all PIs was tested qualitatively in various solvents (approximately 10 mg/5 mL).

Ion conductivity was evaluated using the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy method. LCR bridge Hameg HM8118 was used to accomplish this task. The frequency of the perturbing signal was in the range $200 \text{ kHz} - 20 \text{ Hz}$. The maximal amplitude of the perturbing signal was 50 mV. Resistance of the membrane sample was determined in two electrode arrangement in through plane direction. Mercury was used for contacting the surface of the membrane and Pt wires immersed in mercury have been used to delivery the perturbing signal. Resistance of the membrane was measured in OH^- form and at laboratory temperature (24°C). The membrane was transferred to OH^- form by storing the sample in 0.1 M NaOH at room temperature for 10 days. Resistance of the membrane was evaluated from Nyquist diagram as cross section of the measured points with x-axis. The ion conductivity σ (S m^{-1}) was evaluated following the equation $\sigma = \frac{l}{RS}$, where l stands for thickness of the membrane (m), R represent the membrane resistance (Ω) and S is the geometrical surface of the membrane ($1.57 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2$).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Synthesis and Characterization of (co)polyimides

To prove complete imidization of all prepared PIs the FTIR analysis was used (**Figure 1**). The characteristic absorption bands of the imide group are observed at about 1700 and 1780 cm^{-1} (symmetric and asymmetric stretching of the ring carbonyl groups), the bands at 1020 and 745 cm^{-1} correspond to imide ring deformation, and 1340 cm^{-1} (stretching of the ring C – N bond) whereas the absorption band in the region of 1650 cm^{-1} corresponding to the amide bond of the corresponding PAAs is absent in the spectra of the PI and coPIs, which demonstrates the full imidization. With the growth of pyridine content in the coPI the raise of intensity of the band at 1591 and 1450 cm^{-1} is observed (C=N and C-N pyridine ring stretching). In the spectra of quarternized samples a new peak is observed at 1670 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the C=N⁺ stretching vibration (31)(32), (36).

Figure 1. FTIR spectra of DAP-0, DAP-0.5, DAP-0.5Q

The experimental BIS P/DAP ratio in synthesized coPIs was evaluated using ¹H NMR spectra.

The content of the BIS P and DAP was calculated from ^1H NMR by integrating the signal of 4 protons of BIS P I(a,b,c,d) and proton in *para* position in pyridine ring I(e) (Figure 2A) as follows $\text{DAP}:\text{BIS P} = \text{I(e)}/1\text{H}:\text{I(a,b,c,d)}/4\text{H}$. The calculation confirmed the successful synthesis providing products of the desired composition (Table S1).

Figure 2. ^1H NMR spectrum of DAP-0.2 (A) and DAP-0.3Q (B)

One of the aims of this research was to develop charged coPIs which could form films (membranes) from the solution of volatile organic solvent. Thus, solubility of obtained quarternized copolyimides (coPI-Qs or DAP-Qs) was investigated, see Table 1. With the growth of pyridine content, the solubility of the samples decreases. The coPIs with DAP content more than 50% (DAP-0.6) are brittle insoluble films. Thus, for modification the

samples with lower content of pyridine were chosen, namely, DAP-0.2, DAP-0.3, and DAP-0.5.

Table 1. Solubility of coPIs and modified coPIs

Sample	CHCl ₃	CH ₂ Cl ₂	NMP	DMF	DMSO	CH ₃ CN
DAP-0.6	-	-	-	-	-	-
DAP-0.5	+	-	+	+	-	-
DAP-0.3	+	+	+	+	-	-
DAP-0.2	+	+	+	+	-	-
DAP-0	+	+	-	-	-	-
DAP-0.2Q	+	+/-	+	+	+/-	-
DAP-0.3Q	+	+/-	+	+	+/-	+/-
DAP-0.5Q	+/-	+/-	+	+	+/-	+/-

"+" - soluble, "+/-" - partially soluble, "-" - insoluble, "+*" - soluble after heating up to 40°C

After quaternization all synthesized DAP-Qs demonstrated solubility in NMP. However, the films cast from NMP were non-transparent and fragile, containing residual solvent even after solvent removal treatment. The DAP-Qs were also tested for the solubility in chloroform, and it was shown that only DAP-Qs with the content of DAP below 30% were soluble and could form the film. In case of DAP-0.5Q the small fragments of coPI-Q remained insoluble, thus for this sample the solution was filtered prior to casting. For these reasons, chloroform was selected as appropriate solvent. The membranes were casted from the chloroform solution on the glass substrate and kept overnight in the chamber with chloroform vapours in order to allow them for slow drying avoiding the formation of the pores.

3.2. Degree of quaternization and charge distribution

For samples soluble in chloroform, namely DAP-0.2Q, DAP-0.3Q (reaction time 24h), DAP-0.2Q2 and DAP-0.3Q2 (reaction time 48h) degree of quaternization (DQ) was calculated from ¹H NMR spectra as follows $I(e)/1H:I(g)/3H$ where *e* is proton in *para*-position in pyridine ring and *g* are three protons of methyl group attached to pyridine nitrogen (**Figure 2B**) (33). The results are given in the **Table 2**.

The DQ was also evaluated from the data obtained by means of energy-dispersive X-Ray spectroscopy (EDX). As a reference element iodine was taken which is absent in initial coPIs and present in coPI-Qs in the form of iodide ion as counter ion against pyridinium. The theoretically calculated atomic percentage of iodine in the samples in case of 100%

conversion of pyridine to pyridinium and the iodine amount experimentally obtained via EDX are presented in the Table 2 as well as calculated DQ of pyridine groups.

Table 2. The content of iodine and degree of quaternization of pyridine

Sample	Iodine at.%theor	Iodine at.% EDX	DQ (EDX)	DQ (NMR)
DAP-0.2Q	3.8	0.44	0.11	0.10
DAP-0.3Q	5.9	0.75	0.12	0.14
DAP-0.5Q	10.0	2.26	0.22	n/a
DAP-0.2Q2	3.8	0.59	0.15	0.19
DAP-0.3Q2	5.9	0.96	0.16	0.17

Both methods show almost the same results. It could be seen the DQ slightly increases with the pyridine content in coPIs and the reaction time. However, the DQ for all samples is rather moderate, which can be explained by tangled access of quaternizing agent to the reaction centres caused by low flexibility of rigid pyridine containing fragments.

The distribution of the charge (cations) in the polymer was evaluated by elemental mapping of iodine using energy-dispersive X-Ray spectroscopy (EDX).

Figure 3. Energy dispersive X-Ray spectroscopy elemental maps of Iodine in DAP-0.3 (A), DAP-0.2Q (B), DAP-0.3Q (C), DAP-0.5Q (D)

Figure 3 demonstrates the homogeneous distribution of the iodine atoms in the bulk of modified coPIs, indicating uniform charge distribution throughout the polymer.

Both methods reveal that DQ grows both with increase of pyridine content and reaction time.

3.3. Thermal properties of coPIs and modified coPIs

Thermal properties of the coPIs and modified coPIs were explored by means of TGA and DSC. The graphs of the thermal degradation of the coPIs and modified coPIs are given in the **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. TGA curves of coPIs (A), DSC curves of coPIs (B) and TGA curves of modified coPIs (C)

The loss of 10% of the weight (T_{D10} in Table. 3) occurs at 480°C for all coPIs. The weight loss between 200 and 300°C can be the result of evaporation of residual solvent (the residual NMP is present in the NMR of the coPIs), and/or eventually incomplete imidization (37).

Table 3. Thermal properties of coPIs and modified coPIs

Sample	T_{D10} , °C	T_{1st} , wt. %	I_{EDX} wt. %	T_g , °C
DAP-0	518	-	-	242
DAP-0.2	482	-	-	265
DAP-0.3	492	-	-	257
DAP-0.5	484	-	-	251
DAP-0.2Q	514	6	3,9	n/a
DAP-0.3Q	245	12	7,2	n/a
DAP-0.5Q	291	20	17,3	n/a
DAP-0.2Q2	208	24	5,03	n/a
DAP-0.3Q2	205	27	8,47	n/a

T_{D10} – temperature of 10% weight loss, T_{1st} – weight loss at the end of the first stage of weight loss in the temperature range 200 – 300°C, I_{EDX} – Iodine content according to EDX results, T_g – glass transition temperature.

Modified coPIs don't show noticeable weight loss up to 200°C, then the first stage weight loss from 10 to 20% is observed in the temperature range 200 – 300°C, the lower temperature of the weight loss can be explained by the weaker intermolecular interactions structure of the coPI-Q. The main weight loss stage for all the modified samples starts at around 500°C and is similar to coPIs. The thermal stability of the pyridinium containing polymers is highly dependent on the counter-ion nature, and often the earlier degradation is induced by the counter-ion at much lower temperature than backbone destruction. For the modified coPIs the first stage of weight loss around 250°C is similar for the sample DAP-0.2Q but with the growth of the pyridinium content the weight loss increases respectively due to the probable loss of iodide anions (38), (39). The weight loss at the first stage of thermal degradation correlates with the iodine content according to EDX data (T_{1st} and I_{EDX} columns in Table 3). The modified coPIs do not undergo thermal destruction under 100 °C which is important for their performance in AEM WE with working temperature around 80 °C.

All the coPIs demonstrate higher T_g than DAP-0. It can be the result of incorporation of “rigid” pyridine fragments into the backbone. At the same time T_g decreases in the row of coPIs DAP-0.2>DAP-0.3>DAP-0.5 with the growth of pyridine content. Considering that thermal destruction of the modified coPIs starts at around 200 °C the T_g value for modified coPIs was not acquired.

3.4. Morphology

Morphology of the coPI films and modified coPI membranes was investigated by SEM both on the surface and at the cross section.

Figure 5. SEM images of surface (A-C) and cross-section (D-G) of DAP-0.2Q (A, D), DAP-0.3Q (B, E), DAP-0.5Q (C, G).

All samples are dense films both surface and cross section SEM images (**Figure 5**) reveal the absence of pores or scratches caused by solvent evaporation. Some pore-like structures are visible for DAP-0.5Q sample in Figure 5C, but this is not confirmed by the cross-section image. This indicates that the pore-like structures are not connected and their occurrence is probably connected with solvent evaporation. From the cross-section images it is also possible to see that the modified coPIs are structured into layers. Probably, this structure is achieved due to slow solvent removal.

3.5. Alkaline stability and conductivity

Before measuring the conductivity of the DAP-Qs, the $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ membrane samples were immersed into 0.1M NaOH solution for 10 days at $24 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Then the conductivity of the samples was measured and afterwards the samples were explored by FTIR and TGA. After exposure in 0.1 M NaOH DAP-0.5Q lost its integrity while DAP-0.2Q, DAP-0.3Q, DAP-0.2Q2 and DAP-0.3Q2 remained of the same shape. The ionic conductivities of DAP-0.2Q, DAP-0.3Q, DAP-0.2Q2 and DAP-0.3Q2 were 1.2×10^{-3} ; 1.7×10^{-3} ; 1.8×10^{-3} and $23.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S m}^{-1}$, respectively.

DAP-0.3Q2 exhibits the highest ionic conductivity among the samples. This is likely due to its relatively high pyridine content, increased DQ, and as a result the formation of more cationic centres, reaching the percolation level and thus interconnecting individual conductive domains. However, increasing the pyridine content also results in the insolubility of coPI, fragility of films formed from solvents like NMP, and alkaline instability as it was demonstrated by DAP-0.5Q. Therefore, to further enhance ionic conductivity, achieving higher DQs for the DAP-0.3 sample is essential. Regarding the postpolymerization modification approach used in this research to synthesize coPI-Q, the most straightforward method to increase DQ would be to extend the reaction time. As shown in Table 3, for DAP-0.2, extending the reaction time from 24 hours to 48 hours increases the DQ from 0.10 to 0.19. However, for DAP-0.3, the increase is less significant, rising from 0.14 to 0.17 over the same period. Thus, enhancing the DQ for DAP-0.3 requires a more complex approach and further research.

The chemical structure and thermal properties of coPI-Qs after alkaline treatment were investigated *via* FTIR and TGA. On the FTIR spectra (**Figure 6**) the changes are observed at the 1700 and 1780 cm^{-1} (stretching of the ring carbonyl groups), as well as at 1020 and 745 cm^{-1} , which are attributed to imide ring. For the sample DAP-0.5Q those bands are absent on the FTIR spectrum, which shows the degradation of the polymer backbone. DAP-0.2Q and DAP-0.3Q preserve all the bands attributed to the PI. Similar behaviour is observed for DAP-0.2Q2 and DAP-0.3Q2 (Figure 6 B).

Figure 6. FTIR spectra of DAP-0.3Q against DAP-Qs after exposure in 0.1M NaOH solution (A) and DAP-0.3Q against DAP-Q2s (B).

For all the samples the band at 1670 cm^{-1} disappeared but the band at 1640 cm^{-1} appeared. This band can be observed on the spectra of all the samples and can be attributed to pyridinium against OH^- as counter ion or carboxyl group formed as a result of PI backbone destruction (40). Regarding those possibilities the TGA of the membranes was performed.

Figure 7. TGA curves of DAP-Qs against DAP-Qs after exposure in 0.1M NaOH solution

On the TGA curves (**Figure 7**) there are two main stages of weight loss: the first stage can be caused by the loss of absorbed water (up to 150°C) followed by pyridinium hydroxide degradation with the maximum weight loss at 250°C (41), while the second stage at 460°C is the common stage for all PIs and coPI-Qs (Figure 4C), which confirms that, DAP-0.2Q, DAP-0.3Q, DAP-0.2Q2 and DAP-0.3Q2 probably did not undergo the polyimide backbone destruction.

4. Conclusion

Cationic coPIs with 2,6 – protected pyridinium fragments in the main chain were synthesized by two-stage thermal imidization followed by postpolymerization modification. The obtained coPIs with the content of pyridinium up to 30% were able to form dense layered membranes from chloroform solution. The obtained coPI-Qs showed no significant weight loss up to 200°C . The increase of pyridine content over 30 % leads to the disintegration of the polymer backbone in alkaline medium even at low NaOH concentration. Relatively low conductivity of DAP-0.2Q, DAP-0.3Q, DAP-0.2Q2 and DAP-0.3Q2 can be the result of low degree of substitution and low content of cations. This statement is partially confirmed by the increase of the conductivity of the DAP-0.3Q2 valued 0.234 Scm^{-1} , which has the highest pyridine content and the highest conductivity value among all the samples explored. The possible way to increase degree of substitution is to facilitate the access to the pyridine in the backbone via

increasing the flexibility of the chain. This can be achieved by using pyridine containing monomer with flexible spacers in 2,6 positions.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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